

α -Aminonitriles⁴ (1a, b) were prepared by dissolving potassium cyanide (0.02 mol) in water (10 ml), then an appropriate aldehyde (0.02 mol) was added and the contents cooled. To it glacial acetic acid (0.02 mol) was added dropwise and the contents kept at room temperature for 1.5 h. The diamine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95% ; 10 ml) was then added and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature overnight, filtered, washed with dilute HCl (5%), dried and crystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using cup-plate method⁵. Out of 29 compounds screened, 13 compounds were found active against *S. aureus* and 12 compounds against *E. coli* (zone of inhibition : 16 to >20 mm). Six compounds containing methylene group (1b series) are more active than the others (1a series). Compounds having 3-nitrophenyl and 3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxyphenyl substituents showed better antibacterial activity.

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References

1. R. R. ASTIK, Ph. D. Thesis, Saurashtra University, 1977 ; J. N. ACHARYA and K. A. THAKER, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 307, 1061 ; J. KLOSA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1962, **56**, 3409.
2. A. FURST and B. L. FREEDLANDER, *J. Biol.*, 1953, **11**, 267 ; *Stanford Med. Bull.*, 1952, **10**, 308 ; K. KRAFT, *Pharmazie*, 1950, **5**, 257.
3. F. TIEMANN, *Chem. Ber.*, 1880, **13**, 382.
4. N. C. DESAI, Ph. D. Thesis, Bhavnagar University, 1982.
5. W. M. M. KIRBY and A. W. BAUER, *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.*, 1966, **45**, 493.